

ASSESSMENT OF PATIENT SATISFACTION REGARDING QUALITY OF CARE PROVIDED BY NURSES IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS

Maryam Liaqat^{*1}, Anam Azmat², Ansa Ahmad³, Sumera Jabeen⁴

^{*1,2,3}Post RN BSN Student, Shaikha Fatima Institute of Nursing & Health Sciences Lahore

⁴Nursing Instructor, Shaikha Fatima Institute of Nursing & Health Sciences Lahore

^{*1}maryamliaqat365@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16886112>

Keywords

Patient satisfaction, Quality of care.

Article History

Received: 16 May, 2025

Accepted: 28 July, 2025

Published: 16 August, 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Maryam Liaqat

Abstract

Background: Patient satisfaction refers to the degree to which a patient needs and expectation are met by the healthcare services they receive. It is a crucial measure of the quality of care provided by healthcare professionals, included nurses. Nurses play a vital role in patient satisfaction, as they are often the primary caregivers and have the most direct interaction with patients. Several factors can influence patient satisfaction with quality of care. Objective: To assess patient satisfaction with the quality of care provided by nurses in tertiary care hospital. Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional design was used to collect the data. The sample consisted of 110 Patients admitted in medical ward of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore and Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore that was chosen with convenience sampling technique by using a closed-ended survey. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 25, and patient satisfaction levels were evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale. Results: This current study explicated the frequency of patient satisfaction with quality of care provided by nurses was emerged to be non-significant, only 1.8% patients were poorly satisfied with quality of care. The majority of patients (69.1%) reported being highly satisfied with nursing care. This indicated that most patients had positive experience with the nursing care provided. The patients at both hospitals experienced similar level of satisfaction with the nursing care provided. It reflects well on systematic nursing practices and suggests equitable care across different institutions. Conclusion: The findings underscore the importance of patient-centered approaches and continue enhancement of nursing services to further elevate care quality and outcomes. Key strengths identified include nurses responsiveness, communication, and clinical competences which align with global findings emphasizing these dimension as crucial to patient satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Nurses are essential to the healthcare system, as they dedicate a considerable amount of time to patient care and deliver roughly 80% of primary care in hospitals. The delivery of exceptional nursing care is a crucial component of overall health care quality. Nurses engage in direct patient care, which encompasses

evaluating their requirements, creating care plans, and administering medications (Alhussin, E. et al., 2024).

The standard of nursing care is an essential element and significantly impacts the health of patients. Quality Nursing Care (QNC) is characterized as "the level of excellence demonstrated in delivering nursing services to patients," which includes five

aspects: staff attributes, care-related activities, required conditions for care, the care environment, and the progress of the nursing process as perceived by patients. Delivering nursing care that aligns with quality standards is vital for guaranteeing that patients obtain superior treatment (Alharbi, H. et al., 2023).

Patient satisfaction within healthcare organizations is a multifaceted and evolving concept. Thus, patient satisfaction can be understood from various perspectives; it reflects the level of contentment with the medical services provided in relation to their desires and anticipations. Swarup asserted that patient satisfaction reflects individual's expectations regarding healthcare services in relation to quality of life, illnesses, and other factors.

Moreover, a patient's distinct viewpoint on satisfaction is influenced by the experience of healthcare providers and the assessment of how well the healthcare services meet their requirements (Siam, B.G.A.R., 2022).

Many factors affect the satisfaction and dissatisfaction that the patient feel in the hospital environment. These elements encompass the admission procedure, diagnostic services, technical assistance, the communication abilities and personal interactions of the doctors along with accessibility and convenience (Umoke, M., 2020).

Effective communication plays a vital role in ensuring patients' satisfaction. It encompasses a range of skills including active listening, empathetic interaction, clear expression and depth in both verbal and non-verbal methods. Mastery of these competencies is fundamental for building trust with patients, ensuring accurate assessments and ultimately improving patient outcomes (Alswaid Z.H. et al. 2024).

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate patient satisfaction regarding the quality of care provided by nurses in a tertiary care hospital located in Lahore. Specifically, the study aims to assess patient satisfaction regarding the quality of nursing care, concentrating on elements like communication, empathy, and responsiveness.

Methodology

The study adopted a cross-sectional design, which provides a snapshot of a specific population at a single

point in time and is commonly used to identify prevailing characteristics within a group (Polit & Beck, 2012). The research was conducted over six months at Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, and Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore, targeting patients aged 18 years and above admitted to general medicine wards, who had received nursing care within the past 24–48 hours, could communicate effectively, and were mentally competent to provide informed consent. Terminally ill patients, those with mental retardation, children, and individuals receiving only palliative care were excluded. The sample size of 110 was calculated using the formula $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$ at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, with participants recruited through convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured, closed-ended questionnaire incorporating a five-point Likert scale to assess patient satisfaction with nursing care quality, categorized as high (>69%), moderate (50–69%), and low (<50%). Demographic variables included hospital, age, gender, marital status, education, and occupation, while research variables focused on patient satisfaction and quality of care. Data collection involved obtaining prior permission from the hospital administration, explaining the study objectives, ensuring voluntary participation, securing informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality and anonymity. Each participant completed the questionnaire within 10–15 minutes. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25, following ethical approval from the IRRAB, Shaikha Fatima Institute of Nursing and Health Sciences, Lahore.

Results

Table 1: Demographic information of participants

Study Variable	Category	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Hospital	Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore	49	44.5
	Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore	61	55.5
Age	<20Year	23	20.9
	20-30 Year	42	38.2
	40Year	45	40.9
Gender	Male	50	45.5
	Female	60	54.5
Marital Status	Single	46	41.8
	Married	54	49.1
	Divorced	10	9.1
Level of Education	Primary	35	23.3
	Secondary	59	39.3
	Beechler degree	49	32.7
	Fourth year	7	4.7
Occupation	Working	62	56.4
	Non working	48	43.6

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the study participants. A total of 110 patients participated, with 55.5% from Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore and 44.5% from Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore. Most participants were aged 20–30 years (38.2%) or 40 years and above (40.9%), while 20.9% were below 20 years of age. Females constituted 54.5% of the sample, and males 45.5%. Regarding marital

status, 49.1% were married, 41.8% single, and 9.1% divorced. In terms of education, 39.3% had secondary education, 32.7% a bachelor's degree, 23.3% primary education, and 4.7% had completed the fourth year. More than half of the participants (56.4%) were employed, while 43.6% were not working.

Table 2 Total score of patient satisfaction with quality of nursing

Level of satisfaction	Frequency	%
Highly satisfied (>69)	76	69.1
Moderately satisfied (50-69)	32	29.1
Poor satisfied (<50)	2	1.8
Total	110	100.0

Table 2 shows the distribution of satisfaction levels among 110 respondents. The majority of patients reported being **highly satisfied** with nursing care, as indicated by 76 individuals (69.1%) falling into the **highly satisfied** category (satisfaction scores >69). A smaller group, 32 respondents (29.1%), expressed being **moderately satisfied** (satisfaction scores between 50 and 69). Only 2 individuals (1.8%) reported being **poorly satisfied** (satisfaction scores <50). This indicates that most patients had positive

experiences with the nursing care provided, with a very small percentage expressing dissatisfaction.

Discussion

Patient satisfaction (PS) represents a key indicator of healthcare quality from the patient's perspective, shaped by a range of interconnected factors. To effectively foster and enhance patient satisfaction, multiple elements must be aligned to establish a

supportive environment that fully upholds and respects patients' rights.

The age distribution in the current study reveals that the largest group of participants is over 40 years old. This finding aligns with the results of a study by (Yan et al., 2022) which reported that 43% of their participants were over 40 years old, suggesting a consistent pattern of engagement among older adults in health-related or professional development studies. However, a contradictory study by (Nilakantam et al., 2021) reported that a higher proportion of younger participants. For instance, found that 50.2% of their sample was between 20–30 years, suggesting a youthful dominance in participation, particularly in technology-driven or undergraduate-oriented programs.

The current study revealed that the largest proportion, 47 individuals (42.7%), have attained only primary education. This pattern is consistent with findings from (Alhussin et al., 2024), who reported that 45.3% of respondents in a rural healthcare utilization study had only primary education, suggesting that low educational attainment remains common in certain populations, especially in low- to middle-income regions. Conversely, some studies have reported a higher prevalence of tertiary education among participants. For instance, (Begum et al., 2022), noted that 52% of participants in their urban health service satisfaction study held a bachelor's degree or higher. These disparities highlight the need for healthcare strategies that are inclusive, culturally sensitive, and tailored to varying educational backgrounds.

Current study highlights that a majority of participants, 62 individuals (56.4%), are currently employed, while 48 participants (43.6%) are not engaged in formal work. This shows that over half of the sample is economically active, which may influence their health-seeking behaviors, access to healthcare, and perspectives on service delivery. This finding aligns with results from (Dinsa et al., 2022), who reported that 58% of their study participants were employed, noting that employment status was positively associated with higher patient satisfaction and healthcare access. In contrast, studies conducted in more economically disadvantaged or rural regions have reported higher unemployment rates among participants. For example, (Alharbi et al., 2023), found that 60% of their study population was

unemployed, which they associated with lower rates of clinic attendance and poorer health outcomes. These results highlight the importance of considering socioeconomic status when designing and delivering healthcare services, especially in terms of affordability, accessibility, and patient education. The results of current study demonstrate overall moderate to high levels of patient satisfaction with nursing care.

These results are consistent with previous findings by (Kruszecka-Krówka et al., 2021), reported that 81.2% of respondents expressed satisfaction with nurses' responsiveness and communication, highlighting these aspects as central to perceived quality of care. In a study conducted in India, (Agostinho et al., 2023), observed that 73% of patients rated nurse communication as good or excellent, emphasizing the global importance of nurse-patient interaction in determining satisfaction.

The relatively lower satisfaction with family involvement is mirrored in (Parizad et al., 2021), who found that only 45% of patients felt their families were adequately included in the care process. Likewise, (Akthar et al., 2023) noted that institutional barriers often limit family-centered care, despite its recognized importance in recovery and emotional well-being.

Moreover, while patient privacy and post-discharge care coordination still received positive ratings in Current study, they were noted as areas needing improvement. This aligns with findings by (Bae, 2023), who reported that only 58% of patients were satisfied with discharge planning and privacy protections. Contrastingly (Labrague, 2024), documented higher satisfaction (82%) in these same domains in a Taiwanese hospital, possibly due to structured discharge protocols and privacy-focused infrastructure.

The overall Satisfaction of patients to recommend the hospital reflects a strong level of trust and satisfaction, reinforcing the notion that the perceived quality of nursing care significantly shapes public perception of healthcare institutions. This is supported by (Emon et al., 2023). which highlight a direct correlation between nursing care quality and hospital recommendation scores, with facilities scoring above 4.0 in nursing satisfaction also ranking in the top quartile nationally for patient loyalty.

The above findings are consistent with those of (Mamić et al., 2024), who found that 71% of patients in a tertiary care hospital reported high satisfaction with nursing care, emphasizing the importance of respectful communication, prompt response to needs, and professionalism in shaping patient experiences. In a comparable study conducted by (Ferreira et al., 2023), 66% of respondents were classified as highly satisfied, 30% as moderately satisfied, and 4% as dissatisfied, closely mirroring the current findings. Their research highlighted that higher satisfaction levels were associated with effective communication, adequate explanation of procedures, and consistent attention from nurses.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study revealed a generally positive perception of nursing care among patients in tertiary care hospitals in Lahore, with the majority expressing moderate to high satisfaction levels. Key strengths identified include nurses' responsiveness, communication, and clinical competence, which align with global findings emphasizing these dimensions as crucial to patient satisfaction. However, areas such as family involvement, individualized care, and discharge planning received only moderate ratings, highlighting the need for targeted quality improvement initiatives.

REFERENCES

Akthar, N., Nayak, S., & Pai, Y. (2023). Determinants of patient satisfaction in Asia: Evidence from systematic review of literature. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, 101393.

Alhussin, E. M., Mohamed, S. A., Hassan, A. A., Al-Qudimat, A. R., Doaib, A. M., & Alhawsawy, E. D. (2024). Patients' satisfaction with the quality of nursing care: A cross-section study. *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*, 20, 100690.

Agostinho, P., Potra, T., Lucas, P., & Gaspar, F. (2023). The nursing practice environment and patients' satisfaction with Nursing Care in a hospital context. *Healthcare*,

Akthar, N., Nayak, S., & Pai, Y. (2023). Determinants of patient satisfaction in Asia: Evidence from systematic review of literature. *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, 23, 101393.

Alharbi, H. F., Alzahrani, N. S., Almarwani, A. M., Asiri, S. A., & Alhowaymel, F. M. (2023). Patients' satisfaction with nursing care quality and associated factors: A cross-section study. *Nursing Open*, 10(5), 3253-3262.

Alhussin, E. M., Mohamed, S. A., Hassan, A. A., Al-Qudimat, A. R., Doaib, A. M., & Alhawsawy, E. D. (2024). Patients' satisfaction with the quality of nursing care: A cross-section study. *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*, 20, 100690.

Bae, S.-H. (2023). Comprehensive assessment of factors contributing to the actual turnover of newly licensed registered nurses working in acute care hospitals: a systematic review. *BMC nursing*, 22(1), 31.

Begum, F., Said, J., Hossain, S. Z., & Ali, M. A. (2022). Patient satisfaction level and its determinants after admission in public and private tertiary care hospitals in Bangladesh. *Frontiers in health services*, 2, 952221.

Dinsa, K., Gelana Deressa, B., & Beyene Salgedo, W. (2022). Comparison of patients satisfaction levels toward nursing care in public and private hospitals, Jimma, Ethiopia. *Nursing: Research and eviews*, 177-189.

Emon, M. M. H., Khan, T., & Alam, M. (2023). Effect of Technology on Service Quality Perception and Patient Satisfaction-A study on Hospitals in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Research and Applied Technology (INJURATECH)*, 3(2), 254-266.

Ferreira, D. C., Vieira, I., Pedro, M. I., Caldas, P., & Varela, M. (2023). Patient satisfaction with healthcare services and the techniques used for its assessment: a systematic literature review and a bibliometric analysis. *Healthcare*,

Kruszecka-Krówka, A., Cepuch, G., Gniadek, A., Smoleń, E., Piskorz-Ogórek, K., & Micek, A. (2021). Selected predictors of parental satisfaction with child nursing care in paediatric wards in Poland—Cross-sectional study. *PLoS one*, 16(11), e0260504.

Labrague, L. J. (2024). Relationship between transformational leadership, adverse patient

- events, and nurse-assessed quality of care in emergency units: The mediating role of work satisfaction. *Australasian Emergency Care*, 27(1), 49-56.
- Mamić, M., Vidić, H., Jovanović, T., Galić, S., Jelinčić, I., & Mikšić, Š. (2024). Croatian translation and validation of the patient satisfaction with nursing care quality questionnaire (PSNCQQ). *Healthcare*. 2024; 12: 888. In.
- Nilakantam, S. R., Madhu, B., Prasad, M., Dayananda, M., Basavanagowdappa, H., Bahuguna, J., & Rao, J. N. (2021). Quality improvement project to assess patient satisfaction towards outpatient services of a tertiary care teaching hospital, South India-A cross-sectional study. *Annals of African medicine*, 20(3), 198-205.
- Parizad, N., Goli, R., Mirzaee, R., Baghaie, R., & Habibzadeh, H. (2021). Satisfaction with nursing care and its related factors in patients with COVID-19: A descriptive correlational study. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 10(1), 437.
- Yan, M., Zhi, M., Xu, Y., Hu, L., & Liu, Y. (2022). Inpatient satisfaction with nursing care and its impact factors in Chinese tertiary hospitals: a cross-sectional study. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(24), 16523.